

Practising Counsellors' Extent of Utilization of Referral Service in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State

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Abstract

This study investigated practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral service in Owerri municipal area of Imo-state. The study was guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses. The ex-post facto design was adopted for the study. A sample of 168 counsellors was drawn out of 242 practising counsellors from school based counsellors and counsellors working in hospitals, immigration, welfare departments of local government council and state ministry of women affairs, Nigerian drug law enforcement agency all in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo state. A structured questionnaire titled Practising Counsellors' Extent of Utilization of Referral Services Questionnaire (PCURSQ) was used for data collection. The data collected were analysed using weighted mean, mean and standard deviation, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and t-test analysis. The result indicated that counsellors use referral services occasionally. The result also indicated a significant difference in counsellors' years of experience and area of practice. Among others, it was recommended that the older practising counsellors should mentor and encourage the upcoming ones, so as to inculcate in them the habit of using referral services when the cases are beyond the area of competence.

Key words: Assessment, Practising counsellors, Referral service, Utilization

Introduction

Every viable profession has to its credit, a teeming population that benefit from their services. Any service which people are reluctant to patronise has the tendency of going moribund. In counselling profession, it is paramount to give clients the best, but the best may not always be available due to limitation in knowledge, skill or experience of some counsellors. When this is the scenario, referral becomes necessary.

Referral service has been defined as one of the counselling services which involve transferring a client to another professional or agency for specialized assistance due to one reason or the other (Oguzie,

Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018). Michael (2007) views referral as a thoughtful recommendation given to a patient for a clinical treatment of serious concerns. According to Akinade (2012), referral is defined as a thoughtful, careful and professional transfer of a client to another professional helper by a counsellor due any of the following reasons, lack of time, interest, experience, sex or even religion. Referral in counselling ensures a continuum along the path of holistic care of a client. It is not a sign of weakness or lack of skill, and it does not in any way connote that a counsellor cannot provide a safe and therapeutic environment for the client, but the counsellor as a matter of ethics must take action that is best for the client. Obi and Oguzie (2019) emphasized that referral is a sign of a counsellors' awareness of personal competence and limitation. Obi and Oguzie further affirm that client referral is an ingenious and special form of termination. Lending support to the above expositions, Singh (2007) advocates counsellors must heed the axiom "do not try to take on everything yourself". In the context of this work, referral in counselling is the process of directing or redirecting a client to an appropriate specialist or agency for definitive treatment.

A referral procedure provides a seamless journey from one professional helper to another so all aspect of the clients' difficulties can be supported. Making approximate referral is a proof of being in professional practice. Clients come from all walks of life and can present with many difficulties. One of the counselling ethical obligations is for counsellors to work within their competence and job description, so it is necessary at times to support the client to find additional sources of support where appropriate. This support is gained when referral is made. Psychological therapies are effective for common mental health problems such as anxiety disorder, delusional problems and depression and clients favour psychological treatment over drug treatment (Kravite, Frank & Feldman, 2006). Counsellors have the obligation to be trained in various skill and technique used as intervention strategies in treating our clients. No clients should ever feel that they are beyond help, so if a client asks a counsellor for help, with debts for instance, then a referral should be made to the appropriate professional who can offer help. The issue of referral is a rigorous but critical one, identifying clients that need intervention and conducting prompt referral to appropriate colleagues, to allied professional or to agencies when needed is integral to the functions of a professional counsellor. This helps to boost the image of the profession because it demonstrates that counsellors know their limit of proficiency and can act in the best interest of their clients.

Singh (2007) highlights situations when a counsellor needs to apply referral to include; when counsellors uncover issues or concerns that are beyond their proficiency, when they feel their personality and the clients are not compatible and is interfering with counselling process. Again, when handling clients who are relatives or professional friends, when clients is hesitant of sharing their issues with the counsellors for whatever reason and finally, when after several counselling sessions the counsellor feels that the relationship has not been effective. A critical look at the above shows that clients occupy a pivotal position and at such the relationship between a counsellor and a client is of paramount importance. In counselling relationship the client's emotional wellbeing and stability is respected and taken seriously. Macleod and McMullen (2016) are of the view that counselling relationship is central to the quality of experience

counsellors possess. Hence, the relationship should be seen as a high priority, and if for any reason there is strain in the relationship, referral remains the best option.

The researchers hope that referral service would greatly enhance the quality of care received by the clients. This is because clients are entitled to best possible care and the counsellor as a matter of professionalism should explore referral options whenever they feel that the client's problem is beyond their professional scope and competence, or that their service is no longer beneficial to the client. This is why the researchers are worried about the utilization of referral service by practising counsellors in giving holistic care to their clients. Since the inculcation and maintenance of desirable behaviours and adjusted wellbeing among clients are the utmost goal of counselling and the achievement of this noble objective is entrusted upon the shoulders of therapists (Oguzie & Nwokolo, 2019; Ezunu, Oguzie, Aigbokhaode & Ezunu, 2020), the need therefore to ascertain practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral service in Owerri municipal area of Imo-state becomes the focal interest of this study.

Statement of the Problem

Collaborative partnership among professionals have always yielded positive outcome in specific circumstances. Referral remains ethical and should be utilised in counselling relationships, but this service undoubtedly has been under utilised. The implication is that some issues handled by counsellors will remain unsolved, and confidence would be lost in the efficacy of therapies so acclaimed. The above scenario will lead to low patronage of counselling services and non expansion of the counselling profession. What makes the counselling profession unique among other mental health profession is the wellness base, developmental approach to mental health. So helping clients to take decisions that will bring them out of problem situation remains the focus of every counsellor. Every available option should be explored in doing this, including referring clients to other professionals, but the question is, does practising counsellors make adequate use of referral services when the need arises, and if yes, to what extent? This becomes the problem of this study.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral service in Owerri municipal area of Imo-state. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

1. Practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral service to other professionals
2. Practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral service based on their years of experience
3. Practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral service based on their area of practice.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of practising counsellors' utilization of referral services to other professionals?
2. What is the extent of practising counsellors' utilization of referral based on their years of experience?
3. What is the extent of practising counsellors' utilisation of referral based on their area of practice?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference on the extent of practising counsellor utilization of referral service to other professionals.
2. There is no significant difference on the extent of practising counsellor utilization of referral service based on their years of experience.
3. There is no significant difference on the extent of practising counsellor utilization of referral service based on their area of practise.

Method

The study employed ex-post facto design. This was because the independent variable counsellor years of experience and area of practice cannot be manipulated by the researchers. A sample of 168 counsellors out of 242 practising counsellors in Owerri municipal council of Imo-State constituted the sample. Simple random sampling technique was used in drawing the sample.

The instruments used for data collection was a Questionnaire titled Practising Counsellors' Extent of Utilization of Referral Services Questionnaire (PCURSQ). PCURSQ consisted of two sections (A and B). Section A was on the counsellors' demographic information such as place of work, years of experience. Section B was a rating scale instrument on PCURSQ with four point response options (Always A), Frequently (FR), Occasionally OC, and Rarely (RA), with a total of 10 items. The instrument was given to an expert in measurement and evaluation and a school based counsellor for validation. The correction and suggestions made by the experts were effected, and that resulted in the inclusion of the demographic information of the participants in section A of the instrument and the final ten items for section B. More so, the instrument was trial tested on fifteen each of the practising counsellor different from that used for the study. The instrument was administered once to the counsellors and the reliability was found after being scored using cronbach coefficient alpha. The reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.83, and this was considered reliable for this study.

The questionnaires were distributed to 168 practising counsellors and 162 were retrieved. The counsellors were classified into years of experience as 1 – 10years, 11 – 20years, 21 and above years. Section B of the instrument was scored as AL – 4points, FR – 3points, OC – 2points and RA -1points. The

data collected were analysed using weighted mean and standard deviation for research questions one and two. The decision level for the weighted mean analysis to arrive at Always, Frequently, Occasional and Rarely was 3.50 to 4.00, 2.50 to 3.49, 1.50 – 2.49, 1.00 to 1.49 respectively. Hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.5 level of significance.

Result

The results of the data analysis are presented in tables below in line with the research questions and hypotheses.

Table 1: Mean response of practising counsellors on the utilization of referral service.

S/ No.	Referral to other Professionals	X	Decision
1	Psychologist	2.10	Occasionally
2	Psychiatrist	2.22	Occasionally
3	Medical Doctor	2.11	Occasionally
4	Nurse	2.41	Occasionally
5	Mental Health Counsellor	1.33	Rarely
6	Family Counsellor	2.01	Occasionally
7	Faith based Organization	2.01	Occasionally
8	School Counsellor	1.72	Occasionally
9	Rehabilitation homes	1.10	Rarely
10	Non Governmental Organization.	1.12	Rarely
	Overall	1.93	Occasionally

As presented in Table 1, the overall mean response of the extent of utilization of referral was 1.93 this indicates that practising counsellors occasionally use referral services for their clients in Imo State.

Table 2: Means and standard deviation of the response of practising counsellors on the utilization of referral services based on years of experience

Years of Experience	N	X	SD
1 – 10 years	57	1.86	0.49
11 – 20 years	62	2.45	0.49
21 and above	43	2.65	0.46
Overall	163	2.30	0.58

Table 2 revealed that practicing counsellors who had 21 and above years of experience was the highest on the utilization of referral followed by 10 – 20 years and 1 – 10 years with mean response of 2.65, 2.45 and 1.86 respectively the inference is that practising counsellors having 21 and above years of experience utilized referral service most, followed by 11 – 20 years and finally 1 – 10 years. The responses were further subjected to the Analysis of variance (ANOVA) in order to ascertain if these were significant differences.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses of Practising Counsellors on the Utilization of Referral Service based on their area of practise.

QUALIFICATION	N	X	SD
School based counsellors	128	2.41	0.56
Other categories of practising counsellors	34	2.21	0.58

Data presented in Table 3 showed that the mean response (2.40) of school based counsellors were greater than the mean response (2.21) of other categories of practising counsellors on the extent of utilization of referral services. The inference is that practising counsellors use referral service more than other categories of practising counsellors. In order to ascertain if this difference is significant, the responses were further subjected to the t-test analysis.

Table 4: Analysis of variance response of practising counsellors on the extent of their utilization of referral service based on years of experience

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig (p-value)	Decision
Corrected Model	1770.087	2	885.044	38.600	.000	.
Intercept	85171.889	1	85171.889	3714.6	.00	.
Experience	1770.087	2	885.044	13	.000	
Error	3645.690	159	22.929	38.600		
Total	90838.00	162				
Corrected total	5415.778	161				

R squared =.327 (adjusted R squared =.318) * =Significant at P<0.5 alpha level.

As presented in table 4, the calculated probability value (p-value) .000 for experience is less than the alpha level of 0.5 therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected this implies that there is significant difference on the extent of practising counsellors utilization of referral services based on their years of experience Data in Table 4; also showed a multiple regression squared index (R²) of .327. The inference is that 32.7% of this total variance in the utilization of referral service can be attributable to the influence of practising counsellors' years of experience.

To find the direction of significance, the response were subjected to scheffe's multiple comparison of group means test for a post hoc analysis as in table 5;

Table 5: Result of scheffe's post Hoc test from multiple comparison of group mean based on years of experience of practising counsellors' extent of utilization of referral services.

(i) Experience (J)		Mean		Sig
Experience		Diff (I - J)	Std. Error	@ P,.5
1 – 10 years	11- 20 years	-0.59	.879	.000
	21 and above	-0.79	.967	.000
	1 – 10 years	-0.59	.879	.000
11 – 20 years	21 and above	-0.21	.950	.101
	1 – 10 years	0.79	.967	.00
	11 – 20 years	0.21	.950	.101
21 and above				

*= Significant at P<0.5 alpha level

Table 6: t-test Analysis of practising counsellor utilization of referral service based on their area of practice.

QUALIFICATION	N	X	SD	DF	t	sig	dec
School based counsellors	128	24.05	5.64	160	2.22	0.28	*
Other categories of practising counsellors	34	22.05	5.81				

*significant at P<.05 alpha level

Table 6 showed that the calculated P- value. 28 is less than the alpha level .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis two is rejected. This implies that there exists significant difference on the extent of practising counsellors' utilization of referral service based on their area of practice.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that practising counsellors use referral services in Imo State occasionally. The occasional use of referral service by counsellors might have been due to low knowledge of the content of referral letter or note as the case may be. It could also be attributed to counsellors not making effort to create relationship with other allied professionals. This is in line with Macleod and Mc Mullen (2016) who stated that individuals receiving counselling service may be more likely to follow up with a mental health referral if it comes from a trusted professional. Counsellors could gain a valuable referral sources by making connection and by educating other health professionals about benefits of counselling.

The findings of the study also showed that practising counsellors who had more experience used referral more than their counterparts who were less experienced was a significance one. This might be attributed to less emphasis that is laid on importance of referral in counselling practice in recent years. The

experience may have provided the practising counsellors with knowledge that client problems are better handled through collaborative effort of professionals. This in agreement with Tallent (2011) which states that, counsellors with experience has a significant influence on their clients and as a result produces a better outcome.

Finally, the findings of the study also revealed that school based practising counsellors significantly utilized referral services more than the other non school based counsellors. This could be attributed to the skills and techniques gained by the counsellors as a result of constant practice coupled with frequent consultation by the students. This is in line with Natwick (2017) which stated that being in regular consultation increases a counsellors' competence. Natwick also suggests that counsellors should have a consultation plan and even consult with other professionals to exchange ideas on appropriate skills to be adopted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Practising counsellors should be encouraged by the Association to use referral services to ensure a better result of their clients' situation.
2. The counselling centres in different schools, counselling association both at the chapter and National level should organize special training on the writing referral letters, as this could result in using the service frequently.
3. Older practising counsellors should mentor and encourage the upcoming ones so as to inculcate in them the habit of using referral services when the case is beyond their area of competence.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study and the discussion that followed, it was concluded that practising counsellors in Owerri Municipal council of Imo – State Occasionally utilize referral service. It was also concluded that experienced counsellors used referral service more than their inexperienced counterparts. Finally, the study concluded that school based practising counsellors significantly utilize referral service more than the other non school based counsellors.

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